

PEDAGOGY AS A MAIN FACTOR IN AN EDUCATIONAL ASPECT

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Abstract:

Pedagogy is a term that refers to the method of how teachers teach, in theory and in practice. Pedagogy is formed by an educator's teaching beliefs and concerns the interplay between culture and different ways to learn. In order to help students build on prior learning, meaningful classroom relationships must exist. This article describes about some definitions and characteristics about pedagogy in scientific field.

Key words: pedagogy, educational practice, learning space.

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Pedagogy most commonly caught on as the approach to instructing, is the hypothesis and hone of learning, and how this prepare impacts, and is affected by, the social, political, and mental advancement of learners. Instructional method, taken as an scholarly teach, is the ponder of how information and abilities are bestowed in an instructive setting, and it considers the intuitive that take put amid learning. Both the hypothesis and hone of instructional method shift significantly as they reflect diverse social, political, and social settings.

Pedagogy is frequently portrayed as the act of instructing. The instructional method received by instructors shapes their activities, judgments, and educating procedures by taking into thought hypotheses of learning, understandings of understudies and their needs, and the foundations and interface of person understudies. Its points may extend from advancing magnanimous instruction (the common advancement of human potential) to the smaller specifics of professional instruction (the giving and securing of particular aptitudes). Ordinary western pedagogies see the instructor as information holder and understudy as the beneficiary of information, but speculations of instructional method progressively recognize the understudy as an specialist and the instructor as a facilitator. The meaning of the term "instructional method" is frequently challenged and a awesome assortment of definitions has been proposed. The foremost common approach is to characterize it as the ponder or science of educating strategies. In this sense, it is the methodology of education. As a methodology, it investigates the ways and practices that can be used to realize the aims of education. The main aim is often identified with the transmission of knowledge. Other aims include fostering skills and character traits. They include helping the student develop their intellectual and social abilities as well as psychomotor and affective learning, which are about developing practical skills and adequate emotional dispositions, respectively.

Pedagogy is closely related to didactics but there are a few contrasts. More often than not, didactics is seen as the more restricted term that alludes primarily to the teacher's part and exercises, i.e. how their behavior is most useful to the method of instruction. Typically,

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one central perspective of instructional method other than other perspectives that consider the learner's viewpoint as well. In this more extensive sense, instructional method centers on "any cognizant movement by one individual outlined to improve learning in another". Learning space or learning setting alludes to a physical setting for a learning environment, a put in which instructing and learning happen. The term is commonly utilized as a more conclusive elective to "classroom", but it may moreover allude to an indoor or open air area, either genuine or virtual. Learning spaces are exceedingly different in utilize, learning styles, arrangement, area, and instructive institution. They bolster a assortment of pedagogies, counting calm consider, inactive or dynamic learning, kinesthetic or physical learning, professional learning, experiential learning, and others. Basic instructional method is both a academic approach and a broader social development. Basic instructional method attests that instructive hones are challenged and shaped by history, that schools are not politically impartial spaces, which instructing is political. Decisions regarding the curriculum, disciplinary practices, student testing, textbook selection, the language used by the teacher, and more can empower or disempower students. It asserts that educational practices favor some students over others and some practices harm all students. It also asserts that educational practices often favor some voices and perspectives while marginalizing or ignoring others. Another aspect examined is the power the teacher holds over students and the implications of this. Its aims include empowering students to become active and engaged citizens, who are able to actively improve their own lives and their communities.

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